

Proposed joint amendments to the Erasmus+ programme

18 February 2026

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Disclaimer:

This document presents the final draft (11/02/2026) of joint proposed amendments to the regulation establishing the Erasmus+ programme for the period 2028-2034, by stakeholder organisations from across the European higher education sector. This document will officially be published on the 18th of February 2026 and is accompanied by a cover note with a list of signatories.

General note:

The table below presents the full set of articles from the draft Erasmus + Regulation in **Column 1**. The recitals are included as well, since they may also benefit from revision. **Column 2** presents new changes highlighting what was erased from the original text. **Column 3** is for comments and arguments supporting the proposed changes.

Strikethrough for deletions and in **bold** for additions. Recitals or articles that have been moved, as well as suggested new additions are highlighted.

Proposed amendments to the regulation establishing the Erasmus+ programme for the period 2028-2034

Recitals

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>(1) The Union needs to support and prepare its people, starting from an early age, with the knowledge, skills and competences needed for success in learning, work, and life. To enable this, the Union needs performing, agile, innovative and inclusive education and training systems, able to nurture, attract and retain talent, to keep up with the pace and scope of the ongoing societal, digital, environmental and economic transformations, respond to the demographic challenges and the society's and economy's skills needs, bridge skills gaps and satisfy industry needs in critical sectors.</p>	<p>Becomes Recital 3</p> <p>The Union needs to support and prepare its people, starting from an early age, with to acquire the knowledge, skills and competences needed for success in learning, work, and life to think critically, learn and participate fully in life and society. To enable this, the Union needs performing, agile, high-quality, innovative, inclusive and socially engaged education and training systems, able to nurture, attract and retain talent to keep up across the Union, as well as to foster international talent circulation. This will support the Union in keeping up with the pace and scope of the ongoing societal, economic, digital and environmental transformations, respond to demographic changes challenges, and the society's and economy's skills needs, bridge skills gaps and satisfy industry needs in critical sectors support learners in developing the</p>	<p>The order of recitals was changed to improve the narrative sequence, first highlighting <i>what the Union is</i> (recital 1) and <i>what values it is built on</i> (recital 2).</p> <p>The suggested wording for Recital 1 (now 3) emphasises that mobility experiences per se enable learners to develop soft skills and democratic competences that strengthen Europe's society and its long-term competitiveness.</p> <p>The phrasing “nurture and foster international talent circulation” was preferred to the original wording in order to underline the potential for mutually beneficial relations with third countries. The original wording could be interpreted as implying a contribution to the “brain drain” affecting other countries.</p>

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	competences needed for personal and professional growth, active citizenship and lifelong learning.	Other minor adjustments were introduced to improve the readability of the text.
(2) The Union is a community of values rooted in Europe's history and identity and anchored in the Treaty on the EU. Understanding those values, including fundamental rights and democracy, is an essential life skill and key to participation in the political debate and decision making. Education and training, youth and sport activities help equip citizens with the skills and competences to thrive, actively and meaningfully participate in democratic life and in the society overall, and help people connect around and defend shared values.	<i>Becomes Recital 1</i> The Union is a community of values rooted in Europe's history and identity and anchored in the Treaty on the EU. Understanding those values, including fundamental rights and democracy, is an essential life skill a core element of citizenship and key to participation in the political debate and decision making. Education and training, youth and sport activities help equip citizens with the skills and competences to thrive, actively and meaningfully, to participate in democratic life and in the society overall , and help people to connect around and defend shared values.	EU values should not be framed as life skills, but as an integral part of the concept of citizenship.
(3) The Union is built on solidarity, both among its citizens and among the Member States. That universal value guides the actions of the Union and provides the unity necessary to cope with societal challenges, which individuals are willing to help address in practice, notably through volunteering.	<i>Becomes Recital 2</i>	
(4) It is essential that all people, irrespective of their personal, social, economic or cultural background, have	It is essential that all people, irrespective of their personal, social, economic or cultural background, are encouraged and have the	This amendment aims to convey the importance of going beyond accessibility,

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<p>the opportunity to participate in a mobility experience abroad from an early age, when values and attitudes are formed and when individuals are most receptive to new experiences and influences. Early exposure to different environments, cultures, languages and ways of life can help to break down stereotypes, promote intercultural understanding, and instil values of respect, tolerance and solidarity, thereby contributing to a more united and harmonious Europe.</p>	<p>opportunity to participate in a mobility experience abroad from an early age, when values and attitudes are formed and when individuals are most receptive to new experiences and influences. Early exposure to different environments, cultures, languages and ways of life can help to break down stereotypes, promote intercultural understanding, and instil values of respect, tolerance and solidarity, thereby contributing to a more united and harmonious Europe.</p>	<p>actively encouraging participation and making visible what often remains invisible.</p>
<p>(5) Building inclusive, cohesive and resilient societies, and sustaining the competitiveness of the Union requires investing in learning opportunities for all, regardless of background and means, in cooperation between Member States and organisations active in the field, and in innovative policy development in the fields of education and training, youth and sport. Such an investment also contributes to strengthening European identity, fundamental rights and values and a more democratic Union.</p>	<p>Building inclusive, cohesive and resilient societies, and sustaining the competitiveness of the Union requires investing in learning opportunities for all, regardless of background and means, in cooperation between Member States, institutions and organisations active in the field, and in innovative policy development in the fields of education and training, youth and sport. Such an investment also contributes to strengthening European identity, fundamental rights and values and a more democratic Union.</p>	<p>The proposed wording does not cover Higher Education Institutions that are also critical actors in policy support.</p>
<p>(6) In line with the EU Preparedness Union Strategy³⁷, preparedness, resilience, participation in democratic life and civic engagement should be fostered through a</p>	<p>In line with the EU Preparedness Union Strategy³⁷, preparedness, resilience, participation in democratic life and civic engagement should be fostered through a</p>	<p>The proposal introduces the concept of “preparedness” in broad terms, which raises concerns among universities. This broader wording risks shifting the</p>

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<p>bottom-up approach, encouraging organisations and institutions to play a key role in fostering digital and media literacy, critical thinking, promoting civic engagement, and learning about democracy and citizenship. People and communities across the EU must engage actively to prevent crises and to be sufficiently prepared to respond to them.</p> <p>37 Joint Communication to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on the European Preparedness Union Strategy (Join/2025/130 final).</p>	<p>bottom-up approach, encouraging organisations and institutions to play a key role in fostering digital and media literacy, critical thinking, promoting civic engagement, and learning about democracy and citizenship. People and communities across the EU shall also be encouraged to actively engage in disaster preparedness and risk reduction, especially in relation to health crises and natural disasters exacerbated by climate change.</p> <p>37 Joint Communication to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on the European Preparedness Union Strategy (Join/2025/130 final).</p>	<p>interpretation of preparedness towards security-driven approaches that fall outside the educational scope of the programme. The proposed amendment seeks to preserve a clear and coherent understanding of preparedness that is appropriate for Erasmus+.</p>
<p>(7) Common areas of action and objectives between the 2021-2027 European Solidarity Corps and Erasmus+ programmes highlight the potential for enhanced synergy and regulatory coherence. Bringing all learning mobility, volunteering, cooperation and active citizenship opportunities together provides a single-entry point to all opportunities offered by the Union for young people and organisations active in</p>		

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<p>the field of youth, allowing for a more coordinated and effective approach, and easier access for potential participants and beneficiaries.</p>		
<p>(8) In this context, it is necessary to establish Erasmus+ 2028-2034, the Union Programme for education and training and also in the fields of youth and sport (the ‘Programme’), as the successor to the 2021-2027 Erasmus+³⁸ and European Solidarity Corps³⁹ Programmes, which encompasses actions in the field of education and training, youth and sport and sets up the European Voluntary Humanitarian Aid Corps.</p> <p><small>38 Regulation (EU) 2021/817 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2021 establishing Erasmus+: the Union Programme for education and training, youth and sport (OJ L 189, 28.5.2021).</small></p> <p><small>39 Regulation (EU) 2021/888 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2021 establishing the European Solidarity Corps Programme (OJ L 202, 8.6.2021).</small></p>		
<p>(9) In a rapidly changing economic, social and geopolitical environment, experience has shown the need for a more flexible multiannual financial framework and Union spending programmes. To that effect, and in line with the objectives of the Erasmus+ programme, the funding should duly consider the evolving policy needs and Union’s priorities as identified in</p>	<p>Stable multi-annual funding shall be secured to preserve the beneficiaries’ ability to design, plan and sustain high-quality mobility and capacity-building initiatives. Nevertheless, in a rapidly changing economic, social and geopolitical environment, experience has shown the need for a more flexible balanced and transparent approach to flexibility in the multiannual</p>	<p>The original wording places strong emphasis on flexibility, with broad references to “relevant documents published by the Commission”, without sufficient clarity on who defines priorities and how these relate to the objectives of the Erasmus+ programme.</p>

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<p>relevant documents published by the Commission, in Council conclusions and European Parliament resolutions, while ensuring sufficient predictability for the budget implementation.</p>	<p>financial framework and Union spending programmes. To that effect, and in line with the objectives of the Erasmus+ programme, a limited and clearly defined share of the funding may be adjusted to reflect evolving policy needs and Union’s priorities as identified in relevant documents published by the Commission duly adopted EU strategies, Council conclusions and European Parliament resolutions, while ensuring sufficient sustainability and predictability for the budget implementation.</p>	<p>While a degree of flexibility is necessary to respond to crises and emerging needs, excessive or undefined flexibility risks undermining predictability, transparency and trust among beneficiaries, particularly in the absence of a dedicated Programme Committee.</p> <p>A lack of funding predictability would also risk undermining programme goals, and especially in relation to inclusion. Fluctuating budgets would make it harder to support students with fewer opportunities. Uncertainty would also increase administrative burden for beneficiaries and for agencies implementing the programme, threaten staff continuity, and discourage long-term partnerships (e.g. joint programmes).</p>
<p>(10) The Programme should support the implementation of the Union of Skills⁴⁰ and the overall strategic frameworks for Union policy cooperation in the fields of education and training, including the policy agendas for school education, higher education, vocational education and training and adult learning, including up-skilling and re-skilling, to allow citizens</p>	<p>The Programme should support the implementation of the European Education Area, the Union of Skills⁴⁰ and the overall strategic frameworks for Union policy cooperation in the fields of education and training. This including includes the policy agendas for school education, higher education, vocational education and training and adult learning, including up-skilling and re-skilling, to allow citizens to develop</p>	<p>Inclusion of the European Education Area as a point of reference, as in previous programmes.</p>

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<p>to develop competences and skills at all stages of their life to thrive in society.</p> <p>40 Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions the Union of Skills (COM/2025/90 final).</p>	<p>competences and skills at all stages of their life to thrive in society.</p> <p>40 Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions the Union of Skills (COM/2025/90 final).</p>	
<p>(11) In line with the EU Youth Strategy⁴¹, the European Youth Work Agenda⁴² and the 2024 Communication on the legacy of the European Year of Youth 2022⁴³, the Programme should support meaningful participation of young people and youth organisations in decision and policy making, youth mainstreaming across policy fields, the validation of non-formal and informal learning, high-quality youth work and competence development of youth workers. The programme will continue to support all young people to participate in learning mobility and non-formal learning mobility, including youth exchanges and youth participation activities, with the objective to engage and empower young people to acquire and develop competences for life and their professional future, to become active citizens and participate in economic, social, cultural, democratic and political life, and to connect them to the European</p>		

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<p>project and contribute to building an inclusive, competitive and resilient Union.</p> <p>41 Resolution of the Council of the European Union and the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on a framework for European cooperation in the youth field: The European Union Youth Strategy 2019-2027 (OJ C 456, ST/14944/2018/INIT, 18.12.2018).</p> <p>42 Resolution of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on the Framework for establishing a European Youth Work Agenda 2020/C 415/01 (OJ C 415, 1.12.2020).</p> <p>43 Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on the European Year of Youth 2022 (COM/2024/1 final, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/txt/?uri=celex:52024dc0001)</p>		
<p>(12) The Programme should support participation in sport and physical activity for all, in line with the EU Work Plan for Sport 2024-2027⁴⁴. Therefore, there is a need to focus, in particular, on grassroots sport, taking into account the important role that sport plays in promoting healthy lifestyles, interpersonal relations, social inclusion and equality as well as building cohesive communities.</p> <p>44 Resolution of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on the European Union Work Plan for Sport (1 July 2024 — 31 December 2027), (OJ C, C/2024/3527, 3.6.2024).</p>		

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	<p>New 12a</p> <p>As part of the Union of Equality, the Programme will address differences in relation to access and use by underrepresented groups in line with Article 21 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, the Strategy for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, the LGBTIQ+ Equality Strategy, the EU Anti-Racism Strategy 2026-2030, and the Roma Strategic Framework for equality, inclusion and participation and the EU Guidelines on Human Rights Defenders. In line with the Roadmap for Women’s Rights and the Gender Equality Strategy, the Programme will also contribute to promote equal opportunities across education and training fields.</p>	<p>This recital positions the Programme's inclusion goals and measures within existing actions and frameworks adopted at EU level, thus providing the necessary terms of reference for an adequate interpretation and implementation of the regulation, especially in relation to Chapter III.</p>
<p>(13) Digital transformation has changed society and the economy with an ever-deepening impact on everyday life and</p>		

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demonstrated the need for higher levels of digital readiness and capacity of education and training as well as the pressing need for digital skills development for all across the Union.		
(14) Formal, informal and non-formal learning play an essential role in addressing climate change, raising awareness and instilling the skills and key competences needed for changing personal behaviours. The Programme will help empowering people to act in their respective communities and build up the needed skills for a successful clean transition, in line with the Clean Industrial Deal.		
(15) The international dimension of the Programme should aim to offer opportunities for learning mobility, cooperation and policy dialogue with third countries not associated to the Programme, building on the experience of predecessor programmes, including to contribute to competitiveness of the Union, while ensuring protection of the Union's economic security interests. To increase the impact of those activities, it is important to enhance synergies between the Programme and Global Europe, taking into account the enlargement of the	The international dimension of the Programme should aim to offer more opportunities for learning mobility, cooperation and policy dialogue with third countries not associated to the Programme, building on the successful experience of predecessor programmes, including to contribute to competitiveness of the Union, while ensuring protection of the Union's economic knowledge security interests. To increase the impact of those activities, it is important to enhance synergies between the Programme and Global Europe, taking into account the enlargement of the Union, the	The suggested wording aims to emphasize the importance of increased investment in the international dimension of Erasmus +, while highlighting the positive impact achieved in this area by predecessor programmes. Explicitly referring to knowledge security, rather than economic security, ensures a more narrowly focused and proportionate approach that is better aligned with the educational nature of the Programme, while preserving openness and international cooperation.

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<p>Union, the Global Gateway Strategy and the education and training, youth and sport policy frameworks.</p>	<p>Global Gateway Strategy and the education and training, youth and sport policy frameworks.</p>	
<p>(16) The Programme should bring candidate countries and potential candidates closer to their goal of acceding to the Union. The Programme should promote stability, partnerships and skills development, with countries in the wider neighbourhood including by enhancing ties with the Mediterranean region. Through cooperation with other countries across the globe, the Programme should as well attract talents worldwide, and shape partnerships notably to promote competitiveness of the Union. The Programme should support countries in modernising their institutions and organisations and, more generally, enhancing the quality and inclusiveness of education, training, youth and sport through international partnerships.</p>	<p>The Programme should bring candidate countries and potential candidates closer to their goal of acceding to the Union. The Programme should promote stability partnerships and mutual learning for institutional and skills development with countries in the wider neighbourhood including by enhancing ties with the Mediterranean region. Moreover, the Programme should cement the ties to long-standing partner countries such as the UK and Switzerland. Through cooperation with other countries across the globe, the Programme should as well attract support talent circulation worldwide and shape partnerships notably based on mutual learning, academic cooperation and shared values and shape partnerships notably to promote competitiveness of the Union. Partnerships funded under each of the Global Europe geographic programmes have the potential to consolidate long-term, trust-based collaborations that serve</p>	<p>Tentative to clarify and rebalance the international dimension of the programme in line with its educational objectives, while strengthening references to long-standing partner countries such as the UK and Switzerland and reframing global cooperation around mutual learning, academic cooperation and shared values.</p> <p>The phrasing “support talent circulation” was preferred to the original wording in order to foreground the potential for mutually beneficially relations with third countries. The original wording could be interpreted as implying a contribution to the ‘brain drain’ affecting other countries.</p> <p>The new wording aims to emphasize collaborative relations and shared goals, avoiding prescriptive terminology while taking into account different contexts and perspectives.</p>

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	<p>mutual interests of Europe and its partners. The Programme should support countries in modernising the development of their institutions and organisations, building on local priorities and contexts. More generally, the Programme should contribute to enhancing the quality, diversity and inclusiveness of education, training, youth and sport through international partnerships.</p>	
<p>(17) The implementation of the Programme should be guided by the principles and values of respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality and the rule of law, and solidarity, as respectively enshrined in Article 2 of the Treaty of the European Union and referred to in the preamble of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union. It is thus essential that all parties involved in the Programme respect those principles and values. The Programme should as well respect the principles set out in the 2017 EU Guidelines for the Promotion and Protection of the Rights of the Child and in Article 9 of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities as well as the Union of Equality strategies.</p>		

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<p>(18) The Programme should encourage participation, in particular of young people, in Europe’s democratic life, including by supporting activities that contribute to citizenship education, nurture skills needed for civic engagement and enable to engage and learn to participate in civic society, thereby raising awareness of European common values, including fundamental rights, facilitating interaction with decision-makers at local, national and European levels and contributing to the process of European integration. The Programme should also support the creation of opportunities and mechanisms for meaningful youth participation.</p>		
<p>(19) The Programme should offer accessible, inclusive and safe opportunities for young people and organisations to show solidarity, helping them support communities and address societal challenges, while gaining valuable experience and skills for their personal growth and employability.</p>	<p>The Programme should offer accessible, inclusive and safe opportunities for young people and organisations to show solidarity, helping them support communities and address societal challenges, while gaining providing them with valuable experience and skills for their personal growth and employability and professional development.</p>	<p>The new phrasing implies a wider scope of skills and competences, related to professional life more broadly. The link to employability remains in connection to professional development.</p> <p>An additional small adjustment was needed for readability and accuracy.</p>
<p>(20) Volunteering, both within and beyond the Union, constitutes a rich experience in a non-formal and informal learning context, enabling young people to show</p>		

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<p>solidarity and engage in activities contributing to address societal and humanitarian challenges while enhancing their personal, socio-educational and professional development, active citizenship, civic participation and employability. The Programme should thus also support “European Solidarity Corps” volunteering actions, including the European Voluntary Humanitarian Aid Corps. Those actions were covered under the European Solidarity Corps programme in the 2021-2027 programming period.</p>		
<p>(21) With a view to enhancing the promotion of solidarity and the visibility of humanitarian aid and development cooperation among European citizens, there is a need to develop solidarity of Member States and third countries associated to the programme with third countries not associated affected by disasters from natural hazards and human-induced risks. The European Voluntary Humanitarian Aid Corps should contribute to a coordinated Union needs-based response and will be implemented in accordance with the rules and procedures laid down in this Regulation.</p>	<p>With a view to enhancing the promotion of solidarity and the visibility of humanitarian aid and development cooperation among European citizens, there is a need to develop solidarity of Member States and third countries associated to the programme with third countries not associated affected by disasters from natural hazards and human-induced risks. The European Voluntary Humanitarian Aid Corps should contribute to a coordinated Union needs-based response and should be complemented by targeted educational support measures for learners affected by conflict, persecution or humanitarian crises, including learners at risk who are unable to safely access education in their country or region of</p>	<p>This amendment ensures that humanitarian aid is not limited to volunteering activities but is complemented by educational support measures targeting learners with an at-risk or refugee(-like) background. These measures are integrated in the additional proposals for Art. 21a and Art21b.</p>

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	<p>origin. This will be implemented in accordance with the rules and procedures laid down in this Regulation.</p>	
	<p>New 21a Erasmus+ should – as far as possible – continue to support higher education institutions and their students and staff from and, also, in countries and regions in crises situations, whether caused by events such as war, natural disasters or undemocratic regimes. Special attention should be paid to students and doctoral candidates, who may not be in the position to continue and conclude their studies in a crisis-affected country.</p> <p>This is to be done as much as possible through the adjusted and flexible use of existing funds and actions eligible for the respective country or region. Where possible and necessary, it may also imply allocation and synergies with additional funds.</p>	<p>Based on the lessons learnt from recent crises, the Erasmus+ programme’s resilience and capacity to respond should be systematically enhanced.</p> <p>Supporting higher education institutions in crisis contexts, as well as students and staff with an at-risk or refugee(-like) background is already a practice in Erasmus+, thanks to the proactive and flexible engagement of colleagues at the European Commission and EACEA, for example, in the context of the invasion of Ukraine and the war in Syria.</p> <p>A more systematic approach would demonstrate Europe’s genuine commitment to academic freedom and to related values such as diversity, equity, and inclusion. It would also acknowledge and bolster the efforts made by higher education institutions.</p> <p>Such support requires consideration of special conditions in existing programme</p>

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		<p>lines, for example flexible deadlines, allowing for prolongations or several grants sequence (e.g. for students to finish their degree), exemptions from mandatory mobility periods (which can be a burden for students, who had already to flee their countries), and lack of the necessary documentation (as e.g. no agreement with the (former) home institution).</p> <p>Evidence on Erasmus+' actual impact and potential can be found in the following report, p14, p48-49.</p> <p>As an example, this article illustrates the challenges Belarussian students are facing.</p>
	<p><i>New 21b</i></p> <p>Erasmus+ shall award scholarships to support students who face persecution, denial of educational rights, or punitive actions due to their active work for human rights and a democratic society.</p> <p>The engagement and activism of the nominee should be in line with European</p>	<p>In addition to the ongoing efforts of the European Parliament and the European Commission to establish a European programme for supporting scholars at risk in MSCA-Horizon, a dedicated action to support at-risk students should be explored. A dedicated scholarship scheme for Human Rights Defenders (HRD) could</p>

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	<p>Union values and principles as laid out in its Treaties.</p>	<p>set an important signal, in Europe and beyond, and underline democratic and human values, at a relatively small financial cost.</p> <p>This would provide a scholarship to achieve a degree to an identified HRD, benefiting:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - students at Bachelor and master's level and doctoral candidates who had already been enrolled in a degree but are prevented from continuing studies. - graduates (usually from a Bachelor or a Master) prevented from accessing a higher degree (usually a Master or a Doctorate). <p>Candidates would be nominated by designated organisations, such as relevant European Union or national bodies, institutions such as universities, human rights organisations in the EU.</p> <p>Together with the proposed “Support to higher education in crises” (21b), this would complement the initiative and efforts of the European Parliament and the European Commission to establish a programme for researchers at risk</p>

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		<p>(MSCA4Ukraine, SAFE), which are supported and strongly welcomed by the HE sector.</p> <p>All these measures demonstrate Europe's support for knowledge building and sharing, education and learning, research and science, democracy and human rights, in a global setting.</p> <p>Programmes for students at risk and HRDs provide a very practical means to support international talent to finish their studies and continue their careers, but potentially also to institutions and societies. As support programmes for researchers at risk show, if safe conditions are met, some of the supported return to engage in post-war recovery, establish inter-institutional collaboration and therefore contribute to capacity building and innovation in their home countries.</p>
(22) Young people, in particular those with fewer opportunities, should continue to be given the chance to have a first time, experience travelling throughout Europe as part of an informal and non-formal educational activity that aims to foster their sense of belonging to the Union and		

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to enable them to discover its cultural and linguistic diversity.		
(23) In the field of sport, through mobility opportunities and capacity building, including cooperation, the Programme should foster common European values, volunteering as well as innovation and skills development in and through sport. The Programme should also promote good governance, safety and integrity in sport, sport diplomacy, support grassroots sports organisations, as well as offer young people across Europe the opportunity to participate in cross-border sports initiatives, fostering personal growth, cultural exchange, solidarity and community engagement.		
(24) The Programme brings a key contribution to the Union of Skills and the European Education Area, laying the foundation to skills and competences formation throughout life and providing a genuine common space for quality education and lifelong learning across borders. The Union of skills aims to step up the efforts to achieve high quality education, training, and lifelong learning through delivering basic and advanced skills, providing opportunities for people to update regularly and acquire new and	The Programme brings a key contribution to the European Education Area and the Union of Skills and the European Education Area , laying the foundation to skills and competences formation throughout life and providing a genuine common space for quality education and lifelong learning across borders. The European Education Area and the Union of Skills aim to step up the efforts to acquire knowledge and achieve high quality education, training, and lifelong learning through delivering basic and advanced skills, providing opportunities for	Acquiring (new) skills and competencies rely on gaining knowledge, which is the primary goal of education. Hence, the European Education Area and the Union of Skills are intertwined in this.

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<p>future-oriented skills, facilitating skills circulation and recruitment by businesses across the EU, and attracting, developing and retaining top talent in Europe. In line with the Union of Skills, the Programme should also reflect the importance of entrepreneurship education and financial literacy.</p>	<p>people to update regularly and acquire new and future-oriented skills, facilitating skills circulation and recruitment by businesses across the EU, and attracting, developing and retaining top talent in Europe. In line with the Union of Skills, the Programme should also reflect the importance of entrepreneurship education and financial literacy.</p>	
<p>(25) It is important to stimulate and widen access to learning, teaching and research on EU, values and citizenship. Fostering a European sense of belonging and commitment is particularly important given the challenges faced today by the Union. The Programme should continue to contribute to learning on European integration matters, including the Union's future challenges and opportunities, to promote debate on those matters and the development of excellence in European integration studies.</p>		
<p>(26) The learning of languages contributes to mutual understanding between people and cultures, and fosters mobility within and outside the Union, as language competences are essential life and job skills. Therefore, the Programme should enhance the learning of languages, including, where relevant, national sign languages. To ensure broad and inclusive</p>		

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<p>access to the Programme, it is important that multilingualism be a key principle in the implementation of the Programme.</p>		
<p>(27) Europe faces a growing challenge in meeting the demand for skilled talent in strategic and evolving sectors like clean and circular technologies, transport, energy, water resilience, healthcare, digital technologies, aerospace and defence. To address this key need, it is essential to develop, attract and retain talented individuals in these fields. In line with the Union of skills, the Programme should among other support EU students to pursue studies in such critical sectors and attract as well top talent to Europe by enhancing the attractiveness of education and training and offering scholarships to students, including through Erasmus Mundus scholarships. This would contribute to address the skills needs for the labour market, including for sectors suffering severe staff shortages.</p>	<p>Europe faces a growing challenge in meeting the demand for skilled talent in strategic and evolving sectors like clean and circular technologies, transport, energy, water resilience, healthcare, digital technologies, aerospace and defence. To address this key need, it is essential to develop, retain and attract and retain talented individuals in these fields. In line with the Union of Skills, the Programme should, among others, support EU students to pursue studies in such critical sectors and attract as well top talent to Europe by enhancing the attractiveness of education and training and offering scholarships to students, including through Erasmus Mundus scholarships. This would contribute to address the skills needs for the labour market, including for sectors suffering severe staff shortages.</p>	<p>Instead of identifying particular sectors, we advise policymakers to focus on supporting competencies for a resilient and dynamic workforce that will enhance competitiveness not only in the short run, but also in the long run, across all economic domains.</p> <p>Limiting the scope of this recital to EU students is in contradiction with other EU policies that underline the need to retain and attract talent.</p>
<p>(28) Cooperation enables exchange of practices and capacity building and thereby leads to better outcomes and performance as well as efficiency gains by pooling resources and knowledge. The Programme should therefore support capacity building measures that enhance</p>	<p>Cooperation enables exchange of practices, innovation and capacity building and, thereby, leads to better outcomes and performance as well as efficiency gains by pooling resources and knowledge. The Programme should therefore support capacity building measures that enhance</p>	<p>Insufficient recognition and post-mobility follow-up reduce the long-term impact of mobility, particularly for disadvantaged participants, supporting the need for cooperation measures that enhance recognition and visibility of learning outcomes.</p>

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<p>cooperation at different levels between institutions and organisations that are active in the fields of education and training, youth and sport. This recognises the fundamental role of institutions and organisations in equipping individuals with the knowledge, skills and competences needed in a changing world and helping institutions and organisations active in the field to adequately fulfil their potential for innovation, creativity and entrepreneurship, in particular within the digital economy.</p>	<p>cooperation at different levels between institutions and organisations that are active in the fields of education and training, youth and sport. This recognises the fundamental role of cooperation in empowering institutions and organisations to equip in equipping individuals with the knowledge, skills and competences needed in a changing world and helping. The Programme should also support institutions and organisations active in the field to adequately fulfil their potential for innovation, creativity and entrepreneurship in particular within the digital economy. In this context, the Programme should support cooperation measures facilitating the recognition and validation of learning outcomes and competences acquired through mobility, also by supporting alumni in articulating and making visible such outcomes and competences.</p>	
<p>(29) The Programme should support long-term strategic cooperation at institutional level to build excellence, competitiveness and attractiveness and generate sustainable and systemic transformation of education and training, youth and sport organisations and institutions, in line with the EU's priorities, including by acting as</p>	<p>Among different cooperation formats, the Programme should also support long-term strategic cooperation at institutional level to build excellence, competitiveness and attractiveness and generate sustainable and systemic transformation of education and training, youth and sport organisations and institutions, in line with the EU's priorities,</p>	<p>The new wording points to the variety of cooperation formats within Erasmus +.</p> <p>The following rephrasing emphasizes the importance of multi- and inter-disciplinary approaches.</p>

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>testbeds for innovative education, training and skills development instruments, supporting cooperation with business and industry. The Programme should continue to support the work of education and training institutions and Member States towards removing remaining barriers to transnational cooperation and multiplying the offer of transnational joint study programmes, contributing towards a joint European Degree⁴⁵.</p> <p><small>45 Council Resolution on a joint European degree label and the next steps towards a possible joint European degree: boosting Europe's competitiveness and the attractiveness of European higher education. (J C, C/2025/2939, 22.5.2025).</small></p>	<p>including by acting as testbeds for innovative education, training and skills development instruments, and by supporting, inter alia, cooperation with business and industry. The Programme should continue to support the work of education and training institutions and Member States towards removing remaining barriers to transnational cooperation and increasing the offer of transnational joint study programmes across all study fields, as well as inter- and multi-disciplinary programmes, contributing towards a joint European Degree⁴⁵.</p> <p><small>45 Council Resolution on a joint European degree label and the next steps towards a possible joint European degree: boosting Europe's competitiveness and the attractiveness of European higher education. (J C, C/2025/2939, 22.5.2025).</small></p>	
<p>(30) The Programme should support the core education mission of the European Universities Alliances to enable systemic impact achieved more efficiently through long-term Union level action, notably to reinforce excellence, reduce fragmentation and increase the attractiveness and inclusiveness of EU higher education systems, develop innovative instruments to increase quality of learning and teaching, develop future oriented skills and competences (such as AI, cybersecurity, sustainability, STEM),</p>	<p>The Programme should support the core education mission of the European Universities Alliances to enable systemic impact achieved more efficiently through long-term Union level action, notably to reinforce excellence, reduce fragmentation and increase the attractiveness and inclusiveness of EU higher education systems, develop innovative instruments to increase quality of learning and teaching, develop future oriented skills and competences (such as AI, cybersecurity, sustainability, STEM), including the sectors</p>	<p>The amendment streamlines the recital while strengthening the case for European Universities Alliances as drivers of systemic impact in higher education. It clarifies their role as testbeds for integrated transnational cooperation, reinforces the focus on excellence, attractiveness, inclusiveness and future-oriented learning and skills, and highlights the importance of complementarity with other Union instruments.</p>

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>including the sectors already identified in the Union of Skills, through relevant and future-proof curricula, pedagogical innovation, joint degrees, lifelong learning, micro-credentials, to nurture and attract talent and facilitate transnational cooperation in education, including with business and industry.</p>	<p>already identified in the Union of Skills, through relevant and future-proof curricula, pedagogical innovation, joint degrees, lifelong learning, micro-credentials, to nurture and attract talent and facilitate transnational cooperation in education, including with business and industry. in fostering deep transnational cooperation to enhance university missions and deliver systemic impact. Alliances should act as testbeds for integrated transnational cooperation across education, research, innovation and service to society, strengthening excellence, attractiveness and inclusiveness, and supporting high-quality and future-oriented learning and skills, including through cooperation with external partners such as business and industry. Their activities should be implemented in complementarity with other Union instruments, in particular the successor to Horizon Europe, the European Competitiveness Fund, and National and Regional Plans, while preserving the Programme’s core educational mission.</p>	
<p>(31) In line with relevant Union frameworks and tools, the Programme should contribute to the development and circulation of skills, including by setting up a basic skills support scheme and</p>	<p>In line with relevant Union frameworks and tools, the Programme should contribute to the development and circulation of skills, including through the establishment of by setting up a basic skills support scheme and</p>	<p>The proposed amendment aims to strengthen coherence with existing Union and intergovernmental commitments on the automatic mutual recognition of qualifications and learning periods abroad.</p>

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>fostering quality assurance, transparency, the recognition of skills, competences and qualifications, their digitalisation, and the validation of non-formal and informal learning, skills management and guidance. In that regard, the Programme should also provide support to contact points and networks at national, and European level that facilitate cross-European exchanges and beyond, and the development of flexible learning pathways between different fields of education and training and youth and across formal and non-formal settings, including through the support of micro-credentials' eco-systems.</p>	<p>by fostering quality assurance, transparency, and the recognition of skills, competences and qualifications (covering learning periods abroad, their digitalisation, and the validation of non-formal and informal learning) as well as skills management and guidance. In that regard, the Programme should also provide support to contact points and networks at national, and European level that facilitate cross-European exchanges and beyond, support the effective implementation of automatic mutual recognition and the development of flexible learning pathways between different fields of education and training and youth and across formal and non-formal settings, including through the support of micro-credentials' eco-systems.</p>	<p>Automatic mutual recognition is a key priority reflected in the Council Recommendation on promoting automatic mutual recognition of higher education and upper secondary education diplomas and the outcomes of learning periods abroad (2018), as well as in the Council Recommendation on a European quality assurance and recognition system in higher education (2025), which together underline the need for trust-based and efficient recognition mechanisms across Europe. Furthermore, the Council Recommendation “Europe on the Move” (2024) emphasises that learning mobility should lead to fully recognised outcomes for all learners. This objective is also reaffirmed at intergovernmental level through the Tirana Communiqué, which calls for the effective implementation of automatic recognition as a cornerstone of mobility. Explicitly referencing automatic mutual recognition in this paragraph would therefore reinforce policy coherence and support the Programme’s objective of facilitating mobility and flexible learning pathways.</p>
<p>(32) User-friendly online platforms and tools for virtual cooperation can play an important role in supporting the delivery of</p>		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>education and training and youth policy in Europe and beyond. To increase the use of virtual cooperation activities, the Programme should support more systematic and coherent use of online platforms. It should as well facilitate and support mobility processes through digitalisation.</p>		
<p>(33) The Programme should be designed to promote inclusion, diversity and equal opportunities by widening access to mobility, volunteering and learning across the Union and beyond, thereby enabling all people to fully benefit from a transformative experience.</p>	<p>The Programme should be designed to promote inclusion, diversity and equal opportunities by widening access to sustainable mobility, volunteering and learning across the Union and beyond, thereby enabling all people to fully benefit from a transformative experience.</p>	<p>In line with SDs 9 and 11 and the EU Mobility Strategy, this amendment underlines the need to further highlight the sustainability dimension across the proposal.</p>
<p>(34) The Programme should provide for a set of measures to facilitate and increase the access for people with fewer opportunities, to remove the obstacles that may prevent such access, including financial ones, and to serve as a basis for further implementation guidance. Those measures include, among other, targeted financial support, accessible learning formats, housing support, preparatory activities and support for participants with fewer opportunities before, during and after their participation within the Programme, user-friendly and accessible</p>	<p>The Programme should provide for a set of measures to facilitate and increase the access for people with fewer opportunities, to remove the obstacles that may prevent such access, including financial ones, and to serve as a basis for further implementation guidance. Those measures include, among other, targeted financial support taking into account the difference of actual living and subsistence costs, accessible learning formats, housing support, preparatory activities and support for participants with fewer opportunities before, during and after their participation within the Programme,</p>	<p>The additional text highlights the urgency to better adjust mobility funding to actual living costs. As highlighted by assessment conducted by the Erasmus4All project, the current country groups are not fit-for-purpose.</p>

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
documents available in different languages, support activities for staff dealing specifically with inclusion and diversity in organisations and raising awareness activities among potential participants with fewer opportunities, including in rural and remote areas. In addition, the Programme should allow to give priority in the grant awarding process to quality projects that actively address the inclusion and involvement of participants with fewer opportunities.	user-friendly and accessible documents available in different languages, support activities for staff dealing specifically with inclusion and diversity in organisations and raising awareness activities among potential participants with fewer opportunities, including in rural and remote areas. In addition, the Programme should allow to give priority in the grant awarding process to quality projects that actively address the inclusion and involvement of participants with fewer opportunities.	
(35) In order to make the Programme more accessible for newcomer organisations and for organisations with smaller administrative capacity and to make the Programme more manageable for beneficiaries, the Programme should reinforce the measures to simplify procedures at all stages.	In order to make the Programme more accessible for newcomer organisations and for organisations with smaller administrative capacity and to make the Programme more manageable for beneficiaries, the Programme should reinforce the measures to simplify and digitalise procedures at all stages, while ensuring support that enables all eligible organisations, regardless of size, to participate effectively in the Programme's actions.	Ensuring a predictable minimum level of support enables organisations with smaller administrative capacity to participate effectively in the Programme and prevents simplification measures from disproportionately benefiting only well-resourced beneficiaries.
(36) This Regulation lays down an indicative financial envelope for the Programme. For the purpose of this Regulation, current prices are calculated by applying a fixed 2% deflator.		

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(37) In view of the diversity of the fields covered by the Programme, the ambition for youth and sport to contribute meaningfully to the Programme's objectives and to reach its target groups, should be maintained.		
(38) Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509 of the European Parliament and of the Council ⁴⁶ applies to this Programme. It lays down the rules on the establishment and the implementation of the general budget of the Union, including the rules on grants, prizes, non-financial donations, procurement, indirect management, financial assistance, financial instruments, budgetary guarantees and protection of the financial interests of the Union.		
(39) In accordance with Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509, Regulation (EU, Euratom) No 883/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council ⁴⁷ , Council Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 2988/95 ⁴⁸ , Council Regulation (Euratom, EC) No 2185/96 ⁴⁹ and Council Regulation (EU) 2017/1939 ⁵⁰ , the financial interests of the Union are to be protected through proportionate measures, including the prevention, detection, correction and		

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<p>investigation of irregularities and fraud, the recovery of funds lost, wrongly paid or incorrectly used and, where appropriate, the imposition of administrative sanctions. In particular, in accordance with Regulation (EU, Euratom) No 883/2013 and (EC, Euratom) No 2185/96 the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF) may carry out investigations, including on-the-spot checks and inspections, with a view to establishing whether there has been fraud, corruption or any other illegal activity affecting the financial interests of the Union. In accordance with Regulation (EU) 2017/1939, the European Public Prosecutor's Office (EPPO) may investigate and prosecute fraud and other illegal activities affecting the financial interests of the Union as provided for in Directive (EU) 2017/1371 of the European Parliament and of the Council⁵¹. In accordance with Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509, any person or entity receiving Union funds is to fully cooperate in the protection of the Union's financial interests, to grant the necessary rights and access to the Commission, OLAF, EPPO and the European Court of Auditors and to ensure that any third parties involved in</p>		

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<p>the implementation of Union funds grant equivalent rights.</p> <p>47 Regulation (EU, Euratom) No 883/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 September 2013 concerning investigations conducted by the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF) and repealing Regulation (EC) No 1073/1999 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Council Regulation (Euratom) No 1074/1999 (OJ L 248, 18.9.2013, p. 1.).</p> <p>48 Council Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 2988/95 of 18 December 1995 on the protection of the European Communities financial interests (OJ L 312, 23/12/1995, p. 1).</p> <p>49 Council Regulation (Euratom, EC) No 2185/96 of 11 November 1996 concerning on-the-spot checks and inspections carried out by the Commission in order to protect the European Communities' financial interests against fraud and other irregularities (OJ L 292, 15.11.1996, p. 2).</p> <p>50 Council Regulation (EU) 2017/1939 of 12 October 2017 implementing enhanced cooperation on the establishment of the European Public Prosecutor's Office ('the EPPO') (OJ L 283, 31.10.2017, p. 1).</p> <p>51 Directive (EU) 2017/1371 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 July 2017 on the fight against fraud to the Union's financial interests by means of criminal law (OJ L 198, 28.7.2017, p. 29).</p>		
<p>(40) In order to simplify requirements for beneficiaries, simplified cost options in the form of lump sums, unit costs and flat rates should be used to the maximum possible extent. Simplified cost options to support learning mobility under the Programme should take into account the living and subsistence costs in the host country. In accordance with national law, Member States should be encouraged to exempt those grants from any taxes and</p>	<p>(40) In order to simplify requirements for beneficiaries, simplified cost options in the form of lump sums, unit costs and flat rates should be used to the maximum possible extent. Simplified cost options to support learning mobility under the Programme should take into account the shall be determined with reference to the actual living and subsistence costs in the host country. In accordance with national law, Member States must exempt those grants</p>	<p>These changes ensure that the amounts calculated consider the actual costs of living and subsistence.</p>

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social levies; grants awarded to individuals by public or private legal entities should be treated in the same manner.	from any taxes and social levies; grants awarded to individuals by public or private legal entities should be treated in the same manner.	
(41) It is appropriate to ensure that the 2021-2027 Programmes are closed correctly, in particular as regards the continuation of multiannual arrangements for their management, such as the financing of technical and administrative assistance. As from 1 January 2028, the technical and administrative assistance should ensure, where necessary, the management of actions that have not been finalised under the 2021-2027 Programmes by 31 December 2027.		
(42) In line with Article 349 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU), the Programme should take into account the specific situation of the outermost regions referred to in that Article, including measures to facilitate their participation to the Programme.		
(43) Pursuant to Article 85 (1) of Council Decision (EU) 2021/1764 ⁵² , persons and entities established in overseas countries and territories are eligible for funding under the Programme subject to the rules and objectives and to any specific		

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<p>arrangement applicable to the Member State to which the relevant overseas country or territory is linked.</p> <p>52 Council Decision (EU) 2021/1764 of 5 October 2021 on the association of the Overseas Countries and Territories with the European Union including relations between the European Union on the one hand, and Greenland and the Kingdom of Denmark on the other (Decision on the Overseas Association, including Greenland) (OJ L 355, 7.10.2021, p. 6–134).</p>		
<p>(44) The Programme is to be implemented in accordance with Regulation (EU) [XXX]* of the European Parliament and of the Council [Performance], which establishes the rules for the expenditure tracking and the performance framework for the budget, including rules for ensuring a uniform application of the principles of ‘do no significant harm’ and gender equality referred to in Article 33(2), points (d), and (f), of Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509 respectively, rules for monitoring and reporting on the performance of Union programmes and activities, rules for establishing a Union funding portal, rules for the evaluation of the programmes, as well as other horizontal provisions applicable to all Union programmes such as those on information, communication and visibility.</p>		
<p>(45) In view to optimise the added value, increase scale and impact of investments,</p>	<p>In view to optimise the added value, increase scale and impact of investments, synergies</p>	<p>Regarding synergies, the amendment clarifies the level of complementarity with</p>

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<p>synergies should be sought in particular between the Programme and other Union funding instruments, including through enabling mechanisms. The Programme should seek as well synergies that strengthen collaboration between education and the private sector.</p>	<p>should be sought in particular between the Programme and other Union funding instruments, including through enabling mechanisms. In this context, the Programme should be designed in complementarity with the other funding instruments, including Horizon Europe, the European Competitiveness Fund, and the National and Regional Plans, with a view to strengthening collaboration across education, research and innovation. In line with the Programme's objectives, the Programme should also seek as well synergies that strengthen collaboration between education and the private sector.</p>	<p>other Union funding instruments. It calls for more explicit and structured synergies between Erasmus+ and other programmes, in particular FP10 and the European Competitiveness Fund, in order to maximise impact and ensure coherent support across education, research and innovation.</p>
<p>(46) The Programme should allow for full and partial association of third countries. The Programme should also support the participation of third countries that are not associated to the Programme where those countries are identified in the work programme, their participation contributes to achieve the objectives of the programme and is essential for the implementation of the action.</p>		
<p>(47) Appropriate and inclusive outreach, publicity of the opportunities supported by the Programme should be ensured at local, national and Union level and should take into account the main target groups</p>		

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<p>of the Programme and, where relevant, a wide variety of other target groups. Furthermore, the Commission and the implementing bodies should facilitate the sharing of good practices and project results and gather feedback on the Programme.</p>		
<p>(48) The Programme should mobilise the potential of former participants in the Erasmus+ Programme and support related activities by encouraging them to promote the Programme.</p>	<p>The Programme should mobilise the potential of former participants in the Erasmus+ Programme and support related activities by encouraging them to promote and support the Programme.</p>	<p>The addition emphasizes the importance of involving Erasmus + alumni, not only promoting but concretely supporting the Programme, its prospective beneficiaries and participants, by engaging in a variety of activities, not limited to promotional campaigns.</p>
<p>(49) Measures should be taken to streamline the management of the Programme and achieve economies of scale including by limiting and reducing the number of national agencies.</p>		
<p>(50) Regulations (EU) 2021/817⁵³ and (EU) 2021/888⁵⁴ should be repealed with effect from 1 January 2028.</p> <p>53 Regulation (EU) 2021/817 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2021 establishing Erasmus+: the Union Programme for education and training, youth and sport and repealing Regulation (EU) No 1288/2013 (OJ L 189, 28.5.2021, p. 1).</p> <p>54 Regulation (EU) 2021/888 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2021 establishing the European Solidarity Corps Programme and repealing Regulations (EU) 2018/1475 and (EU) No 375/2014 (OJ L 202, 8.6.2021, p. 32).</p>		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
(51) In order to ensure continuity in providing support in the relevant policy area and to allow implementation to start from the beginning of the 2028-2034 MFF, this Regulation should enter into force on and apply from 1 January 2028.		

Articles

Chapter I General Provisions		
Article 1 Subject matter		
This Regulation establishes Erasmus+, the Union programme for action in the fields of education and training and also in the fields of youth and sport (the ‘Programme’) and lays down the objectives of the Programme, its budget for the period 2028-2034, the forms of Union funding and the rules for providing such funding. This Regulation also sets up the European Voluntary Humanitarian Aid Corps.		
Article 2 Definitions		
For the purposes of this Regulation, the following definitions apply: (1) ‘adult learner’ means a person who has left or finished initial education and training and engages in formal,		

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<p>non-formal or informal learning, including NEET;</p> <p>(2) ‘adult learning’ means any form of formal, non-formal or informal learning for adults, encompassing opportunities for skills development, upskilling and reskilling for competitiveness, enhancing social cohesion and supporting active participation in society;</p> <p>(3) ‘grassroots sport’ means physical leisure activities practiced regularly at non-professional level by people of all ages for health, educational or social purposes;</p> <p>(4) ‘higher education institution’ means an institution which, in accordance with regional, national, or international law or practice, offers quality assured degrees or other recognised tertiary level qualifications, regardless of what such an establishment is called, or a comparable institution at tertiary level which is considered by the national/regional authorities or the European Commission as eligible to</p>		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>participate in the Programme in the respective territories;</p> <p>(5) ‘higher education student’ means a person enrolled at a higher education institution, including at short-cycle, bachelor’s, master’s or doctoral level or equivalent or a person who recently completed a degree from such an institution;</p> <p>(6) ‘European Voluntary Humanitarian Aid Corps’ refers to volunteering activities that support post-crisis long-term humanitarian aid and development cooperation operations in third countries not associated to the Programme, that are intended to provide needs-based assistance aimed at preventing and alleviating human suffering, and maintaining durable human dignity in the face of crises, and that include actions that aim to reinforce disaster preparedness and disaster risk reduction, link relief, rehabilitation and development and contribute towards strengthening the resilience and capacity of vulnerable or disaster-affected communities to cope with and recover from crises;</p>		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>(7) ‘informal learning’ means learning resulting from daily activities and experiences which is not organised or structured in terms of objectives, time or learning support; it may be unintentional from the learner’s perspective;</p> <p>(8) ‘joint study programme’ means a programme coordinated and offered jointly by different higher education institutions from two or more countries and leading to the award of a joint degree;</p> <p>(9) ‘lifelong learning’ means learning in all its forms, whether formal, non-formal or informal, taking place at all stages in life and resulting in an improvement or update in knowledge, skills, competences and attitudes, including through micro credentials or participation in society from a personal, civic, cultural, social or employment-related perspective, such as the provision of counselling and guidance services; it includes early childhood education and care, general education, vocational education and training, higher education, adult learning, youth work</p>	<p>New7a</p> <p>‘International’- relates to any action involving at least one third country not associated to the Programme.</p> <p>Amendment</p> <p>8) ‘joint study programme’ means a programme an integrated curriculum coordinated and offered jointly by different higher education institutions from two or more countries and leading to the award of a joint degree double/multiple degrees or a joint degree.</p>	<p>Building on the definition by EQAR. See here: https://www.eqar.eu/kb/joint-programmes/definitions/</p>

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>and other learning settings outside formal education and training and it typically promotes cross-sectoral cooperation and flexible learning pathways;</p> <p>(10) ‘learning mobility’ means moving physically to a country other than the country of residence, in order to undertake study, training, teaching, or non-formal or informal learning;</p> <p>(11) ‘non-formal learning’ means learning which takes place outside formal education and training through planned activities in terms of learning objectives and learning time and where some form of learning support is present;</p> <p>(12) ‘people with fewer opportunities’ means people who, for economic, social, cultural, geographical or health reasons or due to their migrant background, or for reasons such as disability or educational difficulties or for any other reason, including a reason that could constitute discrimination under Article 21 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, face obstacles that prevent them from having effective</p>		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>access to opportunities under the Programme;</p> <p>(13) ‘school pupil’ means a person enrolled in a learning capacity at an institution providing general education at any level from early childhood education and care to upper secondary education or a person schooled outside an institutional setting considered by the competent authorities as eligible to participate in the Programme as a school pupil in their respective territories;</p> <p>(14) ‘staff’ means a person who, on either a professional or a voluntary basis, is involved in education, training or non-formal and informal learning at all levels, including sport; it includes academic staff, teachers, trainers, school leaders, youth workers, sport staff, early childhood education and care staff, non-educational staff and other practitioners involved on a regular basis in promoting learning;</p> <p>(15) ‘third country’ means a country that is not an EU Member State;</p> <p>(16) ‘vocational education and training learner’ means a person enrolled in an</p>		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>initial or continuous vocational education and training programme at any level from secondary to post-secondary level or a person who has recently graduated or obtained a qualification from such a programme;</p> <p>(17) ‘volunteering’ means an unpaid activity that addresses societal or humanitarian challenges and has a strong learning component;</p> <p>(18) ‘young people’ in the field of youth means individuals aged between 13 and 30;</p> <p>(19) ‘youth worker’ means a person who, on either a professional or a voluntary basis, is involved in non-formal learning and supports young people in their personal socio-educational and professional development and the development of their competences; it includes persons who plan, steer, coordinate and implement activities in the field of youth.</p>	<p>New15a ‘Transnational’ relates to any action involving at least two countries which are either Member States or third countries (fully or partially) associated to the Programme.</p> <p>New15b ‘Virtual cooperation’ means any form of cooperation using information and communication technology tools to facilitate and support any relevant Programme actions;</p> <p>New 15c ‘Vocational Education and Training’ is to be understood as the education and training</p>	<p>Definitions taken from the Regulation (EU) 2021/817 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2021 establishing Erasmus</p> <p>Definition taken from the Council Recommendation of 24 November on</p>

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
	<p>which aims to equip to young people and adults with knowledge, skills and competences required in particular occupations or more broadly on the labour market.</p>	<p>Vocational Education and Training for sustainable competitiveness, social fairness and resilience 2020/C 417/02.</p>

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
Article 3 Programme objectives		
<p>1. The general objective of the Programme is to contribute to a resilient, competitive, and cohesive Europe by promoting high quality lifelong learning, enhancing skills and competences for life and for jobs for all, while fostering Union values, democratic and societal participation, solidarity, social inclusion and equal opportunities, in the EU and beyond. The Programme shall be a key instrument for building the Union of Skills, developing the European Education Area and supporting the implementation of European strategic cooperation in the fields of education and training, including its underlying sectoral agendas.</p> <p>The Programme will advance youth policy cooperation and further develop the European dimension in sport. The objective is to foster a more inclusive, united, and robust Europe by empowering young people, strengthening community ties, and promoting solidarity through meaningful engagement and cooperation. Sport plays a vital role as a driver for social inclusion, health, education, and community development. By investing in youth, volunteering, and sport, the</p>	<p>The general objective of the Programme is to contribute to a resilient, competitive, and cohesive Europe by promoting high quality lifelong learning, enhancing skills and promote high quality lifelong learning, and personal, educational and professional development, while fostering a sense of European identity and values, democratic and societal participation, active citizenship, solidarity, social inclusion and equal opportunities, in the EU and beyond. Through this core educational mission, the Programme will contribute to a resilient, cohesive and competitive Europe. The Programme shall be a key instrument for developing the European Education Area, building the Union of Skills, and supporting the implementation of European strategic cooperation in the fields of education and training, including its underlying sectoral agendas.</p> <p>The Programme will advance youth policy cooperation and further develop the European dimension in sport. The objective is</p>	<p>The modified text aims to clarify the core mission of the Programme, which is mobility and cooperation in education, while recognising that this should contribute to the EU's wider goals of competitiveness, cohesion and resilience.</p> <p>Developing the European Education Area is listed before building the Union of Skills, to reflect its wider scope and status as a firmly established policy objective.</p> <p>In the second paragraph, the amendment seeks to integrate some of the specific objectives into the general objectives, as their scope and intent are of a more overarching nature.</p>

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>Programme aims to build stronger, more connected societies, encourage civic and democratic engagement, and contribute to social cohesion at all levels.</p>	<p>to foster a more inclusive, united, and robust Europe by empowering young people, strengthening community ties, and promoting solidarity through meaningful engagement and cooperation. Sport plays a vital role as a driver for social inclusion, health, education, and community development. By investing in youth, volunteering, and sport, the Programme aims to build stronger, more connected societies, encourage civic and democratic engagement, and contribute to social cohesion at all levels. The Programme will therefore contribute to foster resilience and support the Union in addressing current and future challenges.</p>	
<p>2. The Programme has the following specific objectives:</p> <p>(a) support the improvement of education, skills and competences with particular regard to their relevance for the labour market as well as to the professional</p>	<p>2a.1 New</p> <p>2. The Programme has the specific objectives to promote:</p> <p>(a) the learning mobility of individuals and groups, and cooperation, quality, inclusion and equity, excellence, creativity and</p>	<p>These amendments aim to clarify the specific objectives of the Programme, which in the initial proposal are presented in a repetitive and unclear manner.</p>

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>development and personal growth of the individual and to their contribution to a competitive, sustainable and cohesive society;</p> <p>(b) foster a sense of European identity and active citizenship, enhance solidarity and active participation in society and democracy, inducing a positive societal impact, greater resilience and better preparedness to anticipate, prevent and respond to risks of different nature;</p> <p>(c) foster quality, inclusion, equity, sustainability, creativity, innovation, excellence and cross-border collaboration, strengthening Europe's attractiveness and competitiveness globally, across all fields of education and training, youth and sport;</p> <p>(d) engage and empower young people to acquire and develop professional and personal competences, to participate actively in society and democracy and connect them to the European project;</p> <p>(e) support policy development, including for circulation of skills, accelerating reforms and modernisation at systems' level, across all fields of education and training, youth and sport, ensuring that</p>	<p>innovation at the level of organisations and policies in the field of education and training;</p> <p>2b.1 New</p> <p>(b) non-formal and informal learning mobility and active participation among young people; cooperation, quality, inclusion, creativity and innovation at the level of organisations and policies in the field of youth, and access to opportunities for engagement in solidarity and humanitarian activities;</p> <p>2c.1 New</p> <p>(c) the learning mobility of sport staff, and cooperation, accessibility, participation, integrity and good governance at the level of sport organisations and sport policies, reinforcing sport's social, educational, and community role through actions that focus on building a fair, inclusive, and sustainable sport system across Europe.</p> <p>(ed) support policy development, including for circulation of skills, accelerating reforms and modernisation at systems' level, across all fields of education and training, youth and sport, ensuring that they are more effective, resilient and inclusive;</p>	<p>The objectives also appear to be of a general nature and, in their current form, do not appropriately belong in this section.</p> <p>The proposed amendment reintroduces the objectives of the Programme currently in force (2021-2027), complementing them with one paragraph from the current proposal (d) and an additional paragraph highlighting the need to protect with an at-risk or refugee(-like) background (e).</p> <p>Elements of the original proposal have been incorporated into the preceding article or into the relevant points of this article, where appropriate.</p>

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>they are more effective, resilient and inclusive;</p> <p>(f) provide young people with easily accessible opportunities for engagement in solidarity and humanitarian activities that induce positive societal changes in the Union and beyond (the latter through setting up the European Voluntary Humanitarian Aid Corps), while improving and properly validating their competences, as well as facilitating their continuous engagement as active citizens;</p> <p>(g) promote the European Sport Model by investing in grassroots sport, especially voluntary activities, ensuring accessibility, promoting participation, protecting integrity, supporting good governance, and reinforcing sport's social, educational, and community role, through actions that focus on building a fair, inclusive, and sustainable sport system across Europe.</p>	<p>2e.1 New</p> <p>(e) safeguard academic freedom and the right to education by ensuring targeted support for students and staff from countries and regions in crisis situations, whether caused by events such as war, natural disasters or undemocratic regimes, in full respect of Union values and applicable Union law.</p> <p>(a) support the improvement of education, skills and competences with particular regard to their relevance for the labour market as well as to the professional development and personal growth of the individual and to their contribution to a competitive, sustainable and cohesive society;</p> <p>(b) foster a sense of European identity and active citizenship, enhance solidarity and active participation in society and democracy, inducing a positive societal impact, greater resilience and better preparedness to anticipate, prevent and respond to risks of different nature;</p> <p>(c) foster quality, inclusion, equity, sustainability, creativity, innovation, excellence and cross-border collaboration, strengthening Europe's attractiveness and</p>	

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
	<p>competitiveness globally, across all fields of education and training, youth and sport;</p> <p>(d) engage and empower young people to acquire and develop professional and personal competences, to participate actively in society and democracy and connect them to the European project;</p> <p>(f) provide young people with easily accessible opportunities for engagement in solidarity and humanitarian activities that induce positive societal changes in the Union and beyond (the latter through setting up the European Voluntary Humanitarian Aid Corps); while improving and properly validating their competences, as well as facilitating their continuous engagement as active citizens;</p> <p>(g) promote the European Sport Model by investing in grassroots sport, especially voluntary activities, ensuring accessibility, promoting participation, protecting integrity, supporting good governance, and reinforcing sport's social, educational, and community role, through actions that focus on building a fair, inclusive, and sustainable sport system across Europe.</p>	

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>3. The Programme objectives shall be pursued through the following pillars, which mainly have either a transnational or an international character:</p> <p>(a) Learning opportunities for all; (b) Capacity building support.</p>	<p>3. The Programme objectives shall be pursued through the following pillars, which mainly have either a transnational or an international character:</p> <p>(a) Learning opportunities for all; (b) Capacity building Cooperation and policy support.</p>	<p>The proposed title brings very different Erasmus+ actions under the umbrella of “Capacity Building”. The same name is also currently used for another action: “Capacity Building projects in higher education”. To avoid confusion among applicants and to reflect the diversity of institutional cooperation types, we suggest using “Cooperation and policy support”.</p>
<h2>Chapter II Scope of Intervention</h2>		
<h3>Section 1 Learning opportunities for all</h3>		
<p>Article 4 Learning mobility and volunteering opportunities</p>		
<p>1. In the field of education and training, the Programme shall support:</p> <p>(a) Learning mobility of higher education students and staff; (b) Learning mobility of vocational education and training learners and staff; (c) Learning mobility of school pupils and staff, including staff in early childhood education and care; (d) Learning mobility of adult learners and staff in adult learning.</p>		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>2. In the field of youth, the Programme shall support:</p> <p>(a) Learning mobility of young people, including DiscoverEU, activities supporting youth participation and learning mobility of youth workers;</p> <p>(b) ‘European Solidarity Corps’ volunteering, including the European Voluntary Humanitarian Aid Corps.</p> <p>3. In the field of sport, the Programme shall support learning mobility of athletes and people active in grassroots sport and learning mobility of sport staff.</p> <p>4. Learning mobility under this Article may be accompanied by:</p> <p>(a) support to teaching and learning about the EU, including European integration, values and citizenship;</p> <p>(b) measures such as language support, preparatory visits, training and virtual cooperation.</p>	<p>(a) support to teaching and learning about the EU, including European integration, values and citizenship;</p> <p>b) measures such as language support, preparatory visits, training and virtual cooperation, awareness raising and incentives for environmentally sustainable mobility practices.</p>	<p>The amendment integrates the possibility for the Programme to incentivize green mobility, in line with the EU mobility agenda.</p>

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
Article 5 Talent and excellence development opportunities		
<p>In the field of education and training, the Programme shall support:</p> <p>(a) Erasmus+ scholarships in strategic educational fields, including in joint study programmes;</p> <p>(b) Erasmus Mundus scholarships;</p> <p>(c) Jean Monnet actions in the field of higher education;</p> <p>(d) Support to the following Jean Monnet institutions pursuing an aim of European interest: the European University Institute, Florence, including its School of Transnational Governance; the College of Europe (Bruges, including its subsidiary in Tirana, and Natolin campuses); the European Institute of Public Administration, Maastricht; the Academy of European Law, Trier; the European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education, Odense; and the International Centre for European Training, Nice.</p>	<p>In the field of education and training, the Programme shall support:</p> <p>(a) Erasmus+ scholarships, co-financed where appropriate by other EU funding instruments, for study programmes with a clear transnational dimension, including in joint study programmes and programmes in educational fields identified as strategic;</p> <p>(b) Erasmus Mundus scholarships;</p> <p>(c) Jean Monnet actions in the field of higher education;</p> <p>(d) Support to the following Jean Monnet institutions pursuing an aim of European interest: the European University Institute, Florence, including its School of Transnational Governance; the College of Europe (Bruges, including its subsidiary in Tirana, and Natolin campuses); the European Institute of Public Administration, Maastricht; the Academy of European Law, Trier; the European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education, Odense; and the International Centre for European Training, Nice.</p>	<p>The amendment highlights the need for the new Erasmus + scholarships to be co-financed by other EU funding instruments (e.g., European Competitiveness Fund; National and Regional Plans), so that this new action is not implemented to the detriment of core activities of the Programme.</p> <p>The amendment also emphasises the relevance of a proven European or international dimension, constituting grounds for the scholarship allocation through Erasmus+.</p> <p>In line with proposed Article 15(a), paragraph 4, the definition and periodic review of the strategic educational fields will be carried out in consultation with the Programme Committee. Stakeholders from the education and training sector should be actively involved in the definition of these strategic fields. Inter- and multi-disciplinary approaches should be encouraged. It is through the interaction of</p>

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
		different disciplines that solutions to complex global challenges can be found.
Section 2 Capacity Building Support	Section 2 Capacity Building Cooperation and Policy Support	The proposed title brings very different Erasmus+ actions under the umbrella of “Capacity Building”. The same name is also currently used for another action: "Capacity Building projects in higher education". To avoid confusion among applicants and to reflect the diversity of institutional cooperation types, we suggest using “Cooperation and Policy Support”.
Article 6 Cooperation among organisations and institutions		
<p>The Programme shall support:</p> <p>(a) Partnerships for cooperation, including small-scale partnerships to foster wider and more inclusive access to the Programme;</p> <p>(b) Partnerships for excellence and innovation, building on the European Universities Alliances, Centres of Vocational Excellence, European Teacher Academies, European School Alliances, Joint study programmes, European Youth Together and Sport Collaborative Alliances.</p>	<p>(b) Partnerships for excellence and innovation, building on including the European Universities Alliances, Centres of Vocational Excellence, European Teacher Academies, European School Alliances, Joint study programmes, European Youth Together and Sport Collaborative Alliances.</p>	

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
Article 7 Cooperation among organisations and institutions		
<p>The Programme shall support:</p> <p>(a) Experimentation, preparation and implementation of the Union’s policy agendas and tools covering skills, education and training, youth and sport ;</p> <p>(b) Programme implementation including synergies with, and support to other Union policies and programmes, online platforms, tools for virtual cooperation and tools to facilitate learning mobility;</p> <p>(c) Dissemination and communication.</p>	<p>New</p> <p>(d) Europe-wide networks which boost stakeholders’ engagement in the Programme.</p>	<p>Much of the success of Erasmus+ in reaching out to grassroots organisations and supporting them in navigating how to engage with the programme hinges on the existence of Europe-wide networks of stakeholders. Such civil society organisations disseminate the programme, explain the functioning, provide spaces for cooperation, connect existing Erasmus+ projects, upscale the work done in particular projects, and simply provide scalability to the entire programme. Structural support for the operations of these networks represents a small part of the Erasmus+ budget yet has a significant impact. This needs to be retained and strengthened in the new programme, hence it must be clear that such support is also intended for boosting cooperation within the programme.</p>
Chapter III Inclusion and Diversity		
Article 8 Support measures for inclusion and diversity		
1. When implementing this Regulation, the Commission, Member States and third countries associated to the Programme		

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shall ensure an inclusive approach across all activities.		
2. The Commission, Member States and third countries associated to the Programme shall take effective measures to promote inclusion, diversity and fairness, solidarity, and equal opportunities, in particular to ensure participation of people with fewer opportunities in the Programme.	The Commission, Member States and third countries associated to the Programme shall take effective measures to promote inclusion, diversity and fairness, solidarity, and equal opportunities, in particular to ensure participation of people with fewer opportunities in the Programme. Inclusion and diversity measures should address specific needs and barriers before, during and in the reintegration phase following participation in the Programme, in order to ensure meaningful and equitable outcomes for all participants.	Evidence from Erasmus Student Network research, including the ESNsurvey – 15th edition (Dias et al., 2024) and the study Inclusive Access and Participation in Erasmus+ Mobility (Kalinova-Schmieder et al., 2025), demonstrates that participants with fewer opportunities face barriers before, during and after mobility. These barriers relate, in particular, to access to information, tailored support measures and the recognition of learning outcomes, thereby supporting the need for a lifecycle approach to inclusion and diversity measures across all phases of participation in the Programme.
3. The Commission shall support access to the Programme from an early age and independent of socio-economic background. To achieve that, it shall ensure the provision of measures to facilitate the participation of people with fewer opportunities, including financial support mechanisms, where relevant.	The Commission shall support access to the Programme from an early age and independent of socio-economic background. To achieve that, it shall ensure the provision of measures to facilitate the participation of people with fewer opportunities, including but not limited to financial support mechanisms, targeted information, guidance, administrative flexibility and tailored support services , where relevant.	The amendment clarifies that facilitating participation of people with fewer opportunities requires a comprehensive set of measures beyond financial support, as non-financial barriers such as access to information, guidance and administrative complexity continue to limit effective participation.
4. The Commission may adjust or may authorise the national agencies referred to		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
in Article 19 to adjust, on the basis of objective criteria, the financial support mechanisms to improve access to people with fewer opportunities.		
5. The costs of measures to facilitate or support the participation of people with fewer opportunities shall not justify the rejection of an application under the Programme.		
6. The national agencies referred to in Article 19 shall develop or update where relevant, national inclusion and diversity action plans, based on the framework, and with particular attention to the specific challenges to access the programme within the national contexts. The national inclusion and diversity plans shall form an integral part of the national agencies' planning documents as referred to in Article 19(2).		
7. The Commission shall monitor on a regular basis the implementation of the inclusion and diversity measures, including the national inclusion and diversity plans.		
Chapter IV Financial Provisions		
Article 9 Budget		
1. The indicative financial envelope for the implementation of the Programme for the	The indicative financial envelope for the implementation of the Programme for the	Europe needs an ambitious and stable Erasmus+ budget. The Commission's

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>period 2028-2034 is set at EUR 40 827 000 000 in current prices</p>	<p>period 2028-2034 is shall be set at a minimum of EUR 60 000 000 000 in current prices.</p>	<p>proposed €40.8 billion for 2028–2034 would barely maintain 2027 activity levels once inflation, rising costs, the integration of the European Solidarity Corps and new responsibilities are taken into account. This would leave very limited scope to expand access, improve quality or deliver on newly agreed priorities, including the mobility targets under Europe on the Move, the consolidation of the European Universities Initiative and Centres of Vocational Excellence, enhanced inclusion of learners with fewer opportunities, and new scholarships in strategic fields. As highlighted in the Draghi report, Europe requires significantly more talent, particularly in strategic sectors, and investing in people through cross-border learning and cooperation is central to Europe’s prosperity, competitiveness and resilience. Erasmus+ is one of the EU’s most cost-effective instruments, delivering long-term returns across competitiveness, skills, cohesion, inclusion and global engagement. For these reasons, the financial envelope should be set at a minimum of €60 billion to ensure the programme can meet political ambitions without reducing participation or quality,</p>

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		<p>while maintaining the predictability needed for institutions and learners across Europe.</p> <p>See also: Joint statement 'A stronger Europe needs a properly funded Erasmus+' (7 January 2026)</p>
	<p>1a New</p> <p>Article 9 - paragraph 1a</p> <p>The indicative distribution of the amount set out in paragraph 1 shall be:</p> <p>(a) EUR 49 800 000 000, representing 83 % of the amount set out in paragraph 1 of this Article, to actions in the field of education and training as referred to in Articles 4 to 7, allocated as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (i) at least EUR 17 230 800 000, representing 34,6 % of the total amount set out in point (a) of this paragraph, to actions as referred to in point (a) of Article 4(1) and to actions as referred to in point (a) of Article 6 carried out in the field of higher education; • (ii) at least EUR 10 707 000 000, representing 21,5 % of the total amount set out in point (a) of this paragraph, to actions as referred to 	<p>Education and training are essential to Europe's long-term prosperity, competitiveness and resilience. Erasmus+ delivers proven European added value across all sectors, supporting skills development, employability, inclusion, civic engagement and cooperation among institutions.</p> <p>Clear indicative minimum allocations across sectors are needed to reflect participation levels, rising implementation costs and the programme's expanded scope compared to 2021–2027. These allocations are based on the assumption of a minimum overall programme budget of EUR 60 billion, which is essential to maintain quality, accessibility and ambition across mobility and cooperation actions.</p>

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	<p>in point (b) of Article 4(1) and to actions as referred to in point (a) of Article 6 carried out in the field of vocational education and training;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (iii) at least EUR 7 569 600 000, representing 15,2 % of the total amount set out in point (a) of this paragraph, to actions as referred to in point (c) of Article 4(1) and to actions as referred to in point (a) of Article 6 carried out in the field of school education; • (iv) at least EUR 2 888 400 000, representing 5,8 % of the total amount set out in point (a) of this paragraph, to actions as referred to in point (d) of Article 4(1) and to actions as referred to in point (a) of Article 6 carried out in the field of adult education; • (v) at least EUR 896 400 000, representing 1,8 % of the total amount set out in point (a) of this paragraph, to Jean Monnet actions as referred to in points (c) and (d) of Article 5; • (vi) at least EUR 8 466 000 000, representing 17 % of the total amount set out in point (a) of this 	<p>A predictable and sufficiently funded envelope enables national agencies and beneficiaries to plan mobility, cooperation projects and support services across the programming period. In higher education, stable investment in mobility and cooperation is critical for institutional capacity, high-quality learning and deep transnational collaboration, including through the European Universities alliances. Minimum allocations also help safeguard core programme actions from erosion by new priorities, inflation or unforeseen policy demands, while still leaving flexibility to respond to emerging needs.</p> <p>Sectoral allocations reinforce the programme's ability to meet political expectations linked to the Union of Skills and the European Education Area, while supporting balanced development and preserving quality and access across education and training.</p>

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	<p>paragraph, to actions that are primarily directly managed and to horizontal activities as referred to in Article 4(4), point (a) and (b) of Article 5, point (b) of Article 6, and Article 7;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (vii) EUR 2 041 800 000, representing 4,1 % of the total amount set out in point (a) of this paragraph, for a margin of flexibility that can be used to support any of the actions referred to in Chapter II; <p>(b) EUR 6 180 000 000, representing 10,3 % of the amount set out in paragraph 1 of this Article, to actions in the field of youth as referred to in Article 4(2), point (b) of Article 6, and point (a) of Article 7;</p> <p>c) EUR 1 140 000 000, representing 1,9 % of the amount set out in paragraph 1 of this Article, to actions in the field of sport as referred to in Article 4(3), point (b) of Article 6, and point (a) of Article 7;</p> <p>(d) at least EUR 1 980 000 000, representing 3,3 % of the amount set out in paragraph 1 of this Article, as a contribution to the operational costs of the national agencies; and</p>	<p>Overall, a structured distribution strengthens transparency, ensures fairness across sectors and supports effective implementation, while enabling Erasmus+ to respond to evolving needs, provided the programme's budget reaches the minimum EUR 60 billion required to deliver these ambitions.</p>

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	(e) EUR 900 000 000, representing 1,5 % of the amount set out in paragraph 1 of this Article, for Programme support.	
<p>2. In addition to the amounts set out in paragraph 1 of this Article, and in order to promote the international dimension of the Programme, an additional financial contribution shall be made available from Regulation (EU) [XXX]* of the European Parliament and of the Council [Global Europe] to support actions implemented and managed in accordance with this Regulation. Such contribution shall be in line with a single programming document drawn up under Regulation (EU) XXX [Global Europe].</p>	<p>In addition to the amounts set out in paragraph 1 of this Article, and in order to promote the international dimension of the Programme, an additional financial contribution of EUR 6 000,000,000 shall be made available from Regulation (EU) [XXX]* of the European Parliament and of the Council [Global Europe] to support actions implemented and managed in accordance with this Regulation. Such contribution shall be in line with a single programming document drawn up under Regulation (EU)XXX [Global Europe].</p>	<p>Although the financial contribution of the Global Europe instrument is yet to be determined, the higher education sector highlights the importance of boosting the international dimension of Erasmus+. The Programme has a proven track record in fostering two-way exchanges of knowledge and practices for mutual interests and building trust. Reflecting the size of the Global Europe proposed budget, the sector calls for a contribution of €6 billion to Erasmus+ to strengthen institutional partnerships, talent circulation and capacity building.</p>
	<p>Article 9 - 2a. New</p> <p>In addition to the amounts set out in paragraph 1 of this Article, and in order to promote the competitiveness dimension of the Programme, an additional financial contribution shall be made available from Regulation (EU) [XXX]* of the European Parliament and of the Council [European Competitiveness Fund] to support actions implemented and managed in accordance with this Regulation. Such contribution shall be in line with a single programming</p>	<p>This amendment clarifies that additional funding from the European Competitiveness Fund may be channelled into Erasmus+ to strengthen the Programme's competitiveness dimension. It ensures coherence by requiring that such contributions are implemented fully in line with the Erasmus+ Regulation, thereby avoiding parallel structures and reducing administrative complexity while enabling targeted support for strategic actions.</p>

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	document drawn up under Regulation (EU) XXX [European Competitiveness Fund].	
3. Appropriations may be entered in the Union budget beyond 2034 to cover the expenses necessary and to enable the management of actions not completed by the end of the Programme.		
4. The financial envelope referred to in paragraph 1 and 2 of this Article and the amounts of additional resources referred to in Article 10 may also be used for technical and administrative assistance for the implementation of the Programme, such as preparatory, monitoring, control, audit and evaluation activities, specific and corporate information technology systems and platforms, information and communication activities, including corporate communication on the political priorities of the Union, and all other technical and administrative assistance or staff-related expenses incurred by the Commission for the management of the Programme.		
	4a New The annual allocations for the Programme shall be distributed in a balanced and even manner across the years 2028–2034, ensuring stability and predictability for learning mobility and cooperation actions.	A balanced annual distribution of the Programme budget across 2028–2034 is important to provide stability and predictability for learning mobility and cooperation actions. Stable yearly allocations allow national agencies and

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
		institutions to plan calls, manage resources and support participants effectively. This helps ensure continuity, maintain quality, avoid disruptions, and maintain equitable access for participants throughout the entire programming period.
Article 10 Additional resources		
1. Member States, Union institutions, bodies and agencies, third countries, international organisations, international financial institutions, or other third parties, may make additional financial or non-financial contributions to the Programme. Additional financial contributions shall constitute external assigned revenue within the meaning of Article 21(2), points (a), (d), or (e) or Article 21(5) of Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509.		
2. Resources allocated to Member States under shared management may, at their request, be made available to the Programme. The Commission shall implement those resources directly or indirectly in accordance with Article 62(1), point (a) or (c) of Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509. They shall be additional to the amount referred to in Article 9(1). Those resources shall be used for the benefit of the Member State concerned. Where the		

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<p>Commission has not entered into a legal commitment under direct or indirect management for additional amounts thus made available to the Programme, the corresponding uncommitted amounts may, at the request of the Member State concerned, be transferred back to one or more respective source programmes or their successors.</p>		
<p><i>Article 11 Alternative, combined and cumulative funding</i></p>		
<p>1. The Programme shall be implemented in synergy with other Union programmes. An action that has received a Union contribution from another programme may also receive a contribution under the Programme. The rules of the relevant Union programme shall apply to the corresponding contribution, or a single set of rules may be applied to all contributions and a single legal commitment may be concluded. If the Union contribution is based on eligible costs, the cumulative support from the Union budget shall not exceed the total eligible costs of the action and may be calculated on a pro-rata basis in accordance with the documents setting out the conditions for support.</p>		
<p>2. Award procedures under the Programme may be jointly conducted</p>		

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<p>under direct or indirect management with Member States, Union institutions, bodies and agencies, third countries, international organisations, international financial institutions, or other third parties ('partners to the joint award procedure'), provided the protection of the financial interests of the Union is ensured. Such procedures shall be subject to a single set of rules and lead to the conclusion of single legal commitments. For that purpose, the partners to the joint award procedure may make resources available to the Programme in accordance with Article 10, or the partners may be entrusted with the implementation of the award procedure, where applicable in accordance with Article 62(1), point (c), of Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509. In joint award procedures, representatives of the partners to the joint award procedure may also be members of the evaluation committee referred to in Article 153(3) of Regulation (EU, EURATOM) 2024/2509.</p>		
<p>Article 12 Implementation and forms of Union funding</p>		
<p>1. The Programme shall be implemented in accordance with Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509, under direct management or under indirect</p>		

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management with entities referred to in Article 62(1), point (c) of that Regulation.		
<p>2. The funds implemented under indirect management in a Member State shall be allocated on the basis of:</p> <p>(a) the population of and cost of living in the Member State concerned;</p> <p>(b) the distance between capitals of Member States;</p> <p>(c) performance, calculated based on the most recent data available.</p>		
<p>3. The Commission shall further specify those criteria and their underlying formulae in the work programmes referred to in Article 15.</p>		
<p>4. Union funding may be provided in any form in accordance with Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509, in particular grants, prizes, procurement, and non-financial donations.</p>		
<p>5. Where Union funding is provided in the form of a grant, funding shall be provided as financing not linked to costs or, where necessary, simplified cost options, in accordance with Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509. Funding may be provided in the form of actual eligible cost reimbursement only where the objectives</p>		

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of an action cannot be achieved otherwise.		
6. For the purpose of Article 153(3) of Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509, the evaluation committee may be composed partially or fully of independent external experts.		
7. Public legal entities, and institutions and organisations in the fields of education and training, youth and sport that have received over 50 % of their annual revenue from public sources over the last two years, shall be considered as having the necessary financial and operational capacity to carry out activities under the Programme. They shall not be required to present further documentation to demonstrate that capacity.		
Chapter V Participation in the Programme		
Article 13 Third countries associated to the Programme		
1. The Programme may be opened to the participation of the following third countries through full or partial association, in accordance with the objectives laid down in Article 3, and with the relevant international agreements or any decisions	1. The Programme may be opened to the participation of the following third countries through full or partial association, in accordance with the objectives laid down in Article 3, and with the relevant international agreements or any decisions adopted under the framework of those agreements and applicable to:	There are very strong and long-standing ties of educational, scientific and institutional cooperation between the Union, the United Kingdom and Switzerland. These partnerships have consistently delivered mutual benefit, high-quality outcomes and alignment with the Union’s objectives and values. To safeguard and further strengthen

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<p>adopted under the framework of those agreements and applicable to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) members of the European Free Trade Association which are members of the European Economic Area, as well as European micro-states; (b) acceding countries, candidate countries and potential candidates; (c) European Neighbourhood Policy countries; (d) other third countries. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) members of the European Free Trade Association which are members of the European Economic Area, as well as European micro-states; (b) acceding countries, candidate countries and potential candidates; (c) European Neighbourhood Policy countries; (d) The UK and Switzerland; (e) other third countries. 	<p>this cooperation, it is important to provide both countries with a clear and accessible pathway to association under Erasmus+. Easier and more predictable access and participation would ensure continuity of learning mobility and institutional cooperation, support talent development and contribute to cooperation within the European Education Area.</p>
<p>2. The association agreements for participation in the Programme shall:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) ensure a fair balance as regards the contributions and benefits of the third country participating in the Programme; (b) lay down the conditions of participation in the programmes, including the calculation of financial contributions, consisting of an operational contribution and a participation fee, to a programme and its general administrative costs; 		

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<p>(c) not confer on the third country any decision-making power in the Programme;</p> <p>(d) guarantee the rights of the Union to ensure sound financial management and to protect its financial interests;</p> <p>(e) where relevant, ensure the protection of security and public order interests of the Union.</p> <p>For the purposes of point (d) , the third country shall grant the necessary rights and access required under Regulations (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509 and (EU, Euratom) No 883/2013, and guarantee that enforcement decisions imposing a pecuniary obligation on the basis of Article 299 TFEU, as well as judgements and orders of the Court of Justice of the European Union, are enforceable.</p>		
	<p>2a New</p> <p>For the UK and Switzerland the Commission shall establish, in accordance with the applicable legal framework, a simplified and expedited procedure for renewing their association. This procedure shall ensure continuity of participation for legal entities established in such countries, minimising administrative disruption to ongoing and future collaborations.</p>	<p>There are very strong and long-standing ties of educational, scientific and institutional cooperation between the Union, the United Kingdom and Switzerland. These partnerships have consistently delivered mutual benefit, high-quality outcomes and alignment with the Union’s objectives and values. To safeguard and further strengthen this cooperation, it is important to provide both countries with a clear and accessible pathway to association under Erasmus+.</p>

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		Easier and more predictable access and participation would ensure continuity of learning mobility and institutional cooperation, support talent development and contribute to cooperation within the European Education Area.
Article 14 Eligibility		
1. Eligibility criteria shall be set to support achievement of the objectives laid down in Article 3, in accordance with Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509.		
2. In award procedures under direct and indirect management one or more of the following legal entities may be eligible to receive Union funding: (a) entities established in a Member State; (b) entities established in an associated third country; (c) international organisations; (d) other entities established in non-associated third countries where the funding of such entities is essential for implementing the action and contributes to the objectives laid down in Article 3.	2. In award procedures under direct and indirect management one or more of the following legal entities may be eligible to receive Union funding and to participate in actions under the Programme: (a) entities established in a Member State; (b) entities established in an associated third country; (c) international organisations; (d) other entities established in non-associated third countries where the funding of such entities is essential and beneficial for implementing the action and contributes to the objectives laid down in Article 3.	Clarifying that eligible entities may both receive Union funding and participate in actions. This strengthens legal certainty across all categories of beneficiaries and helps avoid overly narrow interpretations of eligibility. Refining the provision for entities established in non-associated third countries ensures that participation remains possible where it is justified, beneficial and contributes to the Programme’s objectives, while maintaining appropriate safeguards for Union interests.
3. In addition to Article 168(2) and (3) of Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509, associated third countries referred to in Article 13(1) may, where relevant,		

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participate in and benefit from any procurement mechanisms set in Article 168(2) and (3) of Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509. Rules applicable to Member States shall be applied, mutatis mutandis, to participating associated third countries.		
4. Award procedures affecting security or public order, in particular concerning strategic assets and interests of the Union or its Member States, shall be restricted in accordance with Article 136 of Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509.		
5. The work programme referred to in Article 110 of Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509 or the documents related to the award procedure may further specify the eligibility criteria set out in this Regulation or set additional eligibility criteria for specific actions.		
Chapter VI Programming		
Article 15 Work programme		
The Programme shall be implemented by work programmes referred to in Article 110 Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509.	The Programme shall be implemented by work programmes referred to in Article 110 Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509. Those work programmes shall be adopted in accordance with the procedure laid down in Article 15a of this Regulation.	A structured committee procedure provides an appropriate framework for Member States to contribute to the effective implementation of the Programme, supports consistent interpretation across national contexts, and strengthens trust in decision-making related to priorities, work programmes and

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
		<p>how the Programme is implemented. This approach helps safeguard predictability and coherence throughout the programming period while ensuring transparency and alignment with the Programme's objectives.</p>
	<p><i>New Article 15a – Committee procedure</i></p> <p>1. The Commission shall be assisted by a committee. That committee shall be a committee within the meaning of Regulation (EU) No 182/2011.</p> <p>2. The committee may meet in specific configurations to deal with sectoral issues. Where appropriate, in accordance with its rules of procedure and on an ad hoc basis, external experts, including representatives of relevant stakeholders, may be invited to participate in its meetings as observers.</p> <p>3. The committee shall assist the Commission in the definition and periodic review of the strategic educational fields for Erasmus+ scholarships referred to in Article 5, ensuring transparency and appropriate consultation with relevant stakeholders.</p>	<p>The inclusion of this article maintains continuity with the governance arrangements of the current Programme, where the Committee plays a key role in supporting the Commission. Allowing the committee to meet in sector-specific configurations and, where appropriate, draw on external expertise helps ensure that decisions are well-informed and balanced. Involving the committee in defining and periodically reviewing priority areas for Erasmus+ scholarships ensures transparency and appropriate consultation, strengthening the quality of decision-making and helping to ensure that scholarship priorities are well founded.</p>

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
	4. Where reference is made to this paragraph, Article 5 of Regulation (EU) No 182/2011 shall apply.	
Chapter VII Communication and Dissemination		
Article 16 Information, communication and dissemination		
1. In cooperation with the Commission, the national agencies referred to in Article 19 shall develop a consistent communication strategy with regard to effective outreach and to the dissemination and exploitation of the results of activities supported under the actions they manage within the Programme. The national authorities referred to in Article 18 shall support the national agencies in exploiting the results of projects with high potential for impact.		
2. The national agencies referred to in Article 19 shall assist the Commission in its general task of disseminating information concerning the Programme, including information in respect of actions and activities managed at national and Union level, and its results. National agencies shall inform relevant target groups about the actions and activities undertaken in their respective countries.		

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<p>3. The actions and activities referred to in paragraph 1 and 2 shall be implemented in accordance with Regulation (EU) [XXX]* of the European Parliament and of the Council [Performance] which establishes the rules for the expenditure tracking and the performance framework for the budget, including the rules applicable to all Union programmes regarding information, communication and visibility obligations, including in particular obligations for beneficiaries and implementing partners.</p>		
Chapter VII Management and audit system		
Article 17 Arrangements for indirect management at national level		
<p>1. In accordance with the third subparagraph of Article 157(1) of Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509, the implementation of the Programme under indirect management requires the designation of a national authority and a national agency, as specified in Articles 18 and 19.</p>		
<p>2. The national authority and the national agency shall both be considered as implementing bodies under point (c) of Article 62(1) of the Financial Regulation to the extent of their responsibility for budget</p>		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>implementation tasks as agreed with the Commission, with the national authority retaining principal responsibility towards the Commission for the overall implementation of EU funds by the national agency it designates and supervises as referred to in Article 18(10).</p>		
<p>Article 18 National authority</p>		
<p>1. The Member States and the third countries associated to the Programme shall notify the Commission, through their Permanent Representation or Mission to the European Union, of the public law body designated as the national authority for the purposes of this Regulation, and the person or persons legally authorised to act on its behalf.</p>		
<p>2. The national authority shall designate a national agency for the duration of the Programme and notify the Commission thereof. The national authority shall not designate a ministry as a national agency and the national agency shall be organisationally separate from the national authority.</p>		
<p>3. The national authority shall designate an independent audit body as referred to in Article 21.</p>		

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<p>4. The national authority shall provide the Commission with an appropriate ex ante assessment that the national agency satisfies the minimum requirements set out in Article 157(1) to (5) of Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509 and the Union requirements for internal control standards for national agencies and rules for the management of Programme funds.</p> <p>For the purposes of the first subparagraph, the following arrangements shall apply:</p> <p>(a) for the procedures specifically required by the Commission, including its own and those specified in this Regulation, no ex ante assessment shall be done in line with point (b) of Article 157(7) of Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509;</p> <p>(b) for procedures other than those specified in point (a), the national authority shall make an ex ante assessment, which shall be based on its own controls and audits or on controls and audits undertaken by the independent audit body;</p> <p>(c) where the national agency designated for the Programme is the same as the national agency designated in accordance</p>		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
with Regulations (EU) 2021/817 and (EU) 2021/888, the scope of the ex ante assessment shall be limited to the requirements that are new, unless otherwise justified.		
5. In the event that the Commission rejects the designation of the national agency based on its evaluation of the ex ante assessment, or if the national agency does not comply with the minimum requirements set by the Commission, the national authority shall ensure that the necessary remedial steps are taken to ensure compliance, subject to approval by the Commission, or shall designate another body as national agency. In exceptional cases where a national agency ceases to operate or to exist and the national authority itself carries out budget implementation tasks in accordance with this Regulation and relevant agreements thereunder, it shall be exempted from the ex ante assessment.		
6. The national authority shall provide adequate co-financing, at least equivalent to the contribution referred to in Article 20(5), point (b), for the operations of its national agency to ensure that the		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>Programme is managed in accordance with the applicable Union rules.</p>		
<p>7. The national authority shall ensure that appointments of persons responsible for the management of the national agency are justified by the nature of the action, follow fair and transparent rules and procedures and do not give rise to a conflict of interest. In case of serious concerns about compliance with these principles, the Commission may reject the proposed appointment and request the national authority to ensure that the selection procedure is repeated.</p>		
<p>8. The national authority shall monitor and supervise the budget implementation tasks entrusted to its national agency. It shall inform and consult the Commission in due time prior to taking any decision that may have a significant impact on the management of the Programme and the Programme funds.</p>		
<p>9. The national authority shall, each year, provide the Commission with a report on its monitoring and supervision activities and, where appropriate, a statement on its follow-up to any observations issued by the Commission in response to such report.</p>		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>10. The national authority shall take and retain responsibility for the proper management of the Union funds transferred by the Commission to the national agency in the framework of the Programme.</p>		
<p>11. In the event of any irregularity, negligence or fraud attributable to the national agency, or of serious shortcomings, liabilities or underperformance on the part of the national agency, where any of these instances gives rise to claims by the Commission against the national agency, the national authority shall reimburse and indemnify the Commission for such claims.</p>		
<p>12. In the circumstances referred to in paragraph 11, the national authority may, on its own initiative or at the request of the Commission, revoke the mandate of the national agency. Where the national authority wishes to revoke that mandate for any other justified reason, it shall notify the Commission within a reasonable time before the envisaged date of termination of the mandate. In such cases, the national authority and the Commission shall formally agree on specific and time-limited transition measures.</p>		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>13. In the event of revocation as referred to in paragraph 12, the national authority shall carry out the necessary controls regarding the Union funds entrusted to the national agency whose mandate has been revoked and shall ensure that those funds and all documents and management tools required for the management of the Programme are transferred to the new national agency in an unimpeded manner. The national authority shall provide the national agency whose mandate has been revoked with the necessary financial support to continue to meet its contractual obligations vis-à-vis the beneficiaries of the Programme and the Commission pending the transfer of those obligations to a new national agency. Should there be a transitional period between the revocation of this mandate and the designation of a new national agency as accepted by the Commission, the national authority shall, during such period, be responsible for all the obligations of the national agency as laid out in this Regulation and for all of its outstanding contractual obligations vis-à-vis the beneficiaries of the Programme and the Commission.</p>		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>14. Where a national agency ceases to operate or to exist and no new national agency is designated as a result of the withdrawal of a third country from the Programme, the national authority shall be principally responsible for all the obligations of the national agency and for the fulfilment and closure of all the outstanding contractual obligations vis-à-vis the beneficiaries of the Programme and the Commission.</p>		
<p>15. At the request of the Commission, the national authority shall designate the institutions or organisations, or the types of such institutions and organisations eligible to participate in an action of the Programme in its territory.</p>		
<p>16. The national authority shall promote and facilitate effective synergies and complementarities with other Union, national or regional funds or programmes.</p>		
<p>17. The national authority shall ensure that all necessary and appropriate measures are taken to remove any legal and administrative obstacles to the proper functioning of the Programme, including measures aimed at aligning the status of participants in the Programme with that of other nationals in the same situation or at</p>		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
addressing difficulties in obtaining visas or residence permits.		
Article 19 National agency		
<p>1. The national agency shall:</p> <p>(a) be a body within the meaning of Article 62(1), point (c), (v) or (vi) of Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509 and be governed by the law of the Member State or of the third country associated to the Programme concerned;</p> <p>(b) have the adequate management capacity, staff and infrastructure to fulfil its tasks satisfactorily, ensuring efficient and effective management of the Programme and sound financial management of Union funds;</p> <p>(c) have the operational and legal means to apply the administrative, contractual and financial management rules laid down at Union level;</p> <p>(d) have the requisite expertise to implement effectively the actions in all the sectors of the Programme for which it receives a Union contribution;</p> <p>(e) offer, if required by the Commission, adequate financial guarantees, issued preferably by a public authority, corresponding to the level of Union funds it is called upon to manage.</p>		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>2. The national agency shall adequately plan its tasks for the implementation of the relevant actions as set out in the work programme referred to in Article 15 and the relevant agreements with the Commission, as well as for the information, communication and dissemination activities referred to in Article 16(2).</p>		
<p>3. The national agency shall manage all the stages of the project lifecycle of the Programme actions under its responsibility in accordance with Article 62(1), point (c) of Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509 and the relevant agreements with the Commission.</p>		
<p>4. The national agency shall issue grant support to beneficiaries within the meaning of Article 2, point (5) of Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509 by way of grant agreements as specified by the Commission for the Programme action concerned.</p>		
<p>5. The national agency shall not, without prior written authorisation from the national authority and from the Commission, delegate to a third party any task related to the Programme or budget implementation conferred on it. The national agency shall retain sole</p>		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
responsibility for any tasks delegated to a third party.		
6. The national agency shall, each year, provide its national authority and the Commission with a management declaration, a report and any other documents as required in accordance with Article 158 of Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509.		
7. The national agency shall implement in due time the observations issued by the Commission following its analysis of the yearly management declaration and report and of the independent audit opinion thereon.		
Article 20 European Commission		
1. On the basis of the compliance requirements for national agencies referred to in Article 18(4), the Commission shall review the national management and control systems, using in particular the ex ante assessment provided by the national authority, the national agency's yearly management declaration and the opinion of the independent audit body thereon, and the national authority's yearly report referred to in Article 18(9).		
2. On the basis of the ex ante assessment referred to in Article 18(4), the		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>Commission shall accept, conditionally accept or reject the designation of the national agency. The Commission shall not enter into a contractual relationship with the national agency until it has accepted the ex ante assessment as satisfactory or taken appropriate supervisory measures in accordance with Article 157(5) of Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509. In the event of conditional acceptance, the Commission may apply proportionate precautionary measures to its contractual relationship with the national agency. Where the national agency no longer complies with the minimum requirements, the Commission may suspend its contractual relationship with the national agency until remedial action has been taken to ensure compliance, failing which it may request the national authority to revoke the mandate of the national agency and designate a new one, subject to a positive ex ante assessment.</p>		
<p>3. The Commission shall provide the national authorities and the national agencies with appropriate information and guidance in order to ensure consistent and high-quality implementation and management of the Programme. In</p>		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
particular, it shall specify planning, project management and reporting arrangements and ensure that these arrangements follow simple procedures.		
4. The Commission shall not make Programme funds available to the national agency until it has approved its planning documents in accordance with Article 19(2).		
<p>5. The Commission shall make the following Programme funds available to the national agency:</p> <p>(a) a contribution for grant support for the Programme actions the management of which is entrusted to the national agency;</p> <p>(b) a contribution in support of the national agency's Programme management tasks;</p> <p>(c) if relevant, an additional contribution for actions under Article 7, points (a) and (b).</p>		
6. The Commission shall communicate to the national authority and the national agency the outcome of its analysis and observations on the yearly report and management declaration as referred to in Articles 18(9) and 19(6) and on the audit opinion as referred to in Article 21(2).		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>7. Where the Commission does not accept the yearly management declaration or the independent audit opinion thereon, or in the event of unsatisfactory implementation by the national agency of the Commission's observations, the Commission may implement any precautionary and corrective measures necessary to safeguard the Union's financial interests in accordance with Article 132 of Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509.</p>		
<p>8. The Commission shall encourage and maintain an active dialogue and cooperation with and between the national agencies and the national authorities, including the exchange and transfer of good practice, with a view to improving and ensuring the consistent implementation and management of the Programme. It shall also ensure that appropriate conditions are in place for an effective exchange of information between the Union institutions, national agencies or other bodies and entities implementing the Programme.</p>		
<p>9. The Commission shall deliver the necessary information technology systems to support the implementation of the Programme objectives laid down in</p>		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
Article 3, including for indirect management.		
Article 21 Independent audit body		
<p>1. The independent audit body shall:</p> <p>(a) have the necessary professional competence to carry out public sector audits;</p> <p>(b) ensure that its audits take account of internationally accepted audit standards;</p> <p>(c) not be in a position of conflict of interest with regard to the legal entity of which the national agency forms part; in particular, the independent audit body shall be independent, in terms of its functions, of the legal entity of which the national agency forms part.</p>		
<p>2. The independent audit body shall issue an audit opinion on the yearly management declaration as referred to in Article 158(1) of Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509. It shall form the basis of the overall assurance pursuant to Article 127 of Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2024/2509.</p>		
<p>3. The independent audit body shall give the Commission and its representatives and the Court of Auditors full access to all documents and reports in support of the audit opinion that it issues on the national agency's yearly management declaration.</p>		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
Article 22 Principles of the control system		
1. Programme actions and activities managed by the national agencies. The Commission shall set the minimum requirements for the controls by the national agency and the independent audit body.		
2. The national agency shall be responsible for the primary controls of grant beneficiaries for the actions it manages as set out in the work programmes referred to in Article 15. Those controls shall give reasonable assurance that the grants awarded are used as intended and in compliance with the applicable Union rules.		
3. With regard to the Programme funds transferred to the national agencies, the Commission shall ensure proper coordination of its controls with the national authorities and the national agencies, on the basis of the single audit principle and following a risk-based analysis.		
Chapter IX Transitional and Final Provisions		
Article 23 Repeal		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
Regulation (EU) No 2021/817 and Regulation (EU) No 2021/888 are repealed with effect from 1 January 2028.		
Article 24 Transitional provisions		
1. This Regulation shall not affect the continuation or modification of the actions concerned, until their closure, under Regulations (EU) 2021/817 and (EU) 2021/888, which shall continue to apply to the actions concerned until their closure		
2. The financial envelope for the Programme may also cover technical and administrative assistance expenses necessary to ensure the transition between the Programme and the measures adopted under Regulations (EU) 2021/817 and (EU) 2021/888.		
3. Member States shall ensure at national level the unimpeded transition between the actions carried out under Regulations (EU) 2021/817 and (EU) 2021/888 and those to be implemented under this Programme.		
Article 25 Entry into force and application		
This Regulation shall enter into force on the twentieth day following that of its publication in the Official Journal of the European Union.		

Draft Erasmus + regulation	Amendment	Amendment rationale
<p>It shall apply from 1 January 2028.</p> <p>This Regulation shall be binding in its entirety and directly applicable in all Member States.</p> <p>Done at Brussels,</p> <p>For the European Parliament For the Council The President The President</p>		